

THEOREM OF PYTHAGORAS. FOUR NEW PROOFS

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Abstract. Four new proofs of Pythagoras' theorem are given, the first two of which are derived from the similarity of triangles, and the last two from the similarity of triangles and the calculation of the areas of triangles. Unlike the well-known proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem, the last two proofs were reduced to the case where the product of two algebraic terms is zero. Equating the first term to zero reduced the proof to the general case of the Pythagorean Theorem, and the second term to the special case, which is easy to prove. The Pythagorean Theorem is a good example for the mathematical education of pupils and students, as the number of proofs is not limited. Proofs of this theorem in different ways are very good algebro-geometric exercises. Schools and universities can organise competitions for the greatest number of proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem. These competitions could lead to new proofs of the theorem. All this could develop into a kind of movement called "Pythagoreana", which would be very useful in raising the prestige of mathematical education among young people. This article is a translation of a Russian-language article published under the title "The Pythagorean Theorem. For new evidence" in Scientific Bulletin of Belgorod State University. No. 20 (241), Iss.44, 2016, pp. 34 – 41. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/151231313.pdf> (In Russian).

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One of the greatest achievements of ancient mathematics is the Pythagorean Theorem. It forms the foundation of much of Euclidean geometry and all of trigonometry [1,2], Newtonian physics, and relativistic dynamics [3,4]. For instance, in work [3], it is proven that the Pythagorean Theorem underpins Newton's three laws, the universal law of gravitation, Coulomb's law, and the formulas of relativistic dynamics. For several millennia, this theorem has attracted the close attention of both professionals and enthusiasts.

Our search for various names of the Pythagorean Theorem in English and Russian using the Google Scholar search engine (advanced search with an exact phrase) led to the following results (Table 1).

Table 1

**The appearance of different names for the theorem of Pythagoras. Google Scholar.
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Name	The appearance of names in the text of a scientific publication	The appearance of names in the title of a scientific publication
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Pythagorean Theorem	24,800	353
Pythagoras Theorem	11,200	110
Theorem of Pythagoras	2,730	41
Теорема Пифагора	1,480	15
Пифагорова теорема	11	0
Total	40221	519

From Table 1, we can see that there are approximately 40,000 scientific publications (mostly journal articles) that mention the term "Pythagorean Theorem" in both Russian and English.

The Pythagorean Theorem is often used for educational purposes. For example, in work [5], five traditional proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem are considered for these purposes.

Both new and old proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem can be found in works from the late 19th to early 20th centuries [6,7]. Six new proofs of this theorem were proposed in work [8]. Three new proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem were made as part of a student project at the University of North Florida [9].

Due to the constant increase in the number of proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem, the question of the infinite number of proofs of this theorem was raised in work [10].

The most comprehensive collection of proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem is found in the book [1] published by the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (USA). It is noted that, at the time of the first edition of this book, 230 different proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem were collected (1927), and by the second edition, the number had grown to 370 (1940). In the latter case, 109 algebraic and 225 geometric proofs were highlighted.

Since May 6, 1997, and to the present day, all available proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem have been gathered on the website Cut the Knot Interactive Mathematics Miscellany and Puzzles (www.cut-the-knot.org/pythagoras/index.html). As of December 2015, 114 proofs of the theorem had been collected on the site.

In this regard, it is clear that any new proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem must be tested on the aforementioned website and in the book [1].

Of all the available proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem, the ones that require the least geometric constructions and algebraic calculations are of the greatest interest. In particular, the proof by A.M. Legendre, obtained in 1858 [1,2], satisfies these requirements. Let us present this elegant proof in

the notation of work [2], except for the notation of the height (h). If a perpendicular is drawn to the hypotenuse of a right triangle, dividing it into segments x and y, then, by similarity of the two newly formed right triangles, we obtain the following relations (Fig. 1):

$$\frac{x}{a} = \frac{a}{c} \Rightarrow x = \frac{a^2}{c};$$

$$\frac{y}{b} = \frac{b}{c} \Rightarrow y = \frac{b^2}{c}.$$

Figure 1. Diagram for Legendre's proof and the first new proof of the Pythagorean Theorem.

Given that $x + y = c$, we get:

$$\frac{a^2}{c} + \frac{b^2}{c} = c \Rightarrow a^2 + b^2 = c^2.$$

Which is what we sought to prove.

Another original proof of the Pythagorean Theorem, though somewhat more complex, was provided in 1876 by the 20th President of the United States, James A. Garfield [1,2].

By completing two equal right triangles into a trapezoid, as shown in Figure 2, and calculating the area of the trapezoid in two ways, we obtain:

$$\frac{1}{2}(a + b)(a + b) = \frac{1}{2} ab + \frac{1}{2} ab + \frac{1}{2} c^2 \Rightarrow (a + b)(a + b) = 2ab + c^2 \Rightarrow a^2 + b^2 = c^2.$$

Which is what we sought to prove.

Figure 2. Diagram for Garfield's proof.

In this proof, unlike Legendre's proof, which requires knowledge of the theorem of triangle similarity, only formulas for calculating the areas of a triangle and a trapezoid are used.

Interest in the Pythagorean Theorem has not diminished even in our time. Among the most recent publications, we note works [11-13], with the latest work, published in the *American Mathematical Monthly* in May 2015, offering yet another new proof of the Pythagorean Theorem.

Below, we describe four new proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem.

Four New Proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem

Proof 1. Considering two similar triangles in Figure 1, we can perform the following calculations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{h}{b} = \frac{a}{c} &\Rightarrow a = \frac{hc}{b}; \quad \frac{x}{a} = \frac{h}{b} \Rightarrow x = \frac{ah}{b}; \quad \frac{x}{h} = \frac{h}{c-x} = \frac{h}{c-\frac{ah}{b}} \Rightarrow \\ \frac{x}{h} = \frac{hb}{cb-ah} &\Rightarrow x(cb-ah) = bh^2 \Rightarrow \frac{ah}{b}(cb-ah) = bh^2 \Rightarrow \\ ahc - \frac{a^2h^2}{b} = bh^2 &\Rightarrow \left(\frac{hc}{b}\right)hc - \frac{a^2h^2}{b} = bh^2 \Rightarrow \frac{h^2c^2}{b} - \frac{a^2}{b} = bh^2 \Rightarrow \\ h^2(c^2 - a^2 - b^2) = 0 &\Rightarrow c^2 = a^2 + b^2. \end{aligned}$$

The Pythagorean Theorem is proven.

Proof 2. Placing the cathetus of length a of the original right triangle symmetrically and drawing the altitude on the hypotenuse of the symmetrical triangle, we write down the basic balance equations (Fig.3).

$$h_1 + h_2 = h, \tag{1}$$

$$x + y = c. \tag{2}$$

Figure 3. Diagram for the second new proof of the Pythagorean Theorem.

From the similarity of triangles, we obtain the following relations:

$$\frac{h}{2b} = \frac{a}{c} \Rightarrow h = \frac{2ab}{c}, \tag{3}$$

$$\frac{h}{x} = \frac{a}{b} \Rightarrow x = \frac{hb}{a}. \quad (4)$$

Substituting (3) into formula (4), we get:

$$x = \frac{2b^2}{c}. \quad (5)$$

Again, using the property of triangle similarity, we obtain:

$$\frac{b}{a} = \frac{h_2}{y} = \frac{h_2}{c-x}. \quad (6)$$

Substituting (5) into formula (6), we get:

$$\frac{b}{a} = \frac{h_2}{y} = \frac{h_2}{c - \frac{2b^2}{c}} = \frac{h_2 c}{c^2 - 2b^2} \Rightarrow h_2 = \frac{(c^2 - 2b^2)b}{ac}. \quad (7)$$

Using the property of triangle similarity one last time, we obtain:

$$\frac{h_1}{b} = \frac{c}{a} \Rightarrow h_1 = \frac{cb}{a}. \quad (8)$$

Substituting (7) and (8) into (1), taking (3) into account, we get:

$$\frac{cb}{a} + \frac{(c^2 - 2b^2)b}{ac} = \frac{2ab}{c}. \quad (9)$$

Now, transforming equation (9):

$$\begin{aligned} c^2 b + (c^2 - 2b^2)b &= 2a^2 b \Rightarrow \\ 2c^2 b - 2b^3 - 2a^2 b &= 0 \Rightarrow 2b(c^2 - a^2 - b^2) = 0 \Rightarrow \\ c^2 &= a^2 + b^2. \end{aligned}$$

The Pythagorean Theorem is proven.

In the terminology of work [1], both proofs are algebraic in nature.

Proof 3. Let us construct a square on the hypotenuse of length c directed towards the triangle. Then, the square constructed on the leg of length a will be divided into four triangles with areas S_1 , S_2 , S_3 and S_4 (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Diagram for the third and fourth new proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem.

Among these triangles, we observe a right triangle with area S_1 congruent to the original one with side lengths a , b and c (the proof is obvious). Lengths of cathets and hypotenuse of a right triangle with area S_2 are denoted by x , $a - b$ and y , respectively. Then, the other two right triangles with areas S_3 and S_4 , which form the square with side of length a , will have cathets of lengths a and $a - x$; c and y , respectively.

From the similarity of right triangles, we obtain the relations:

$$\frac{x}{a-b} = \frac{b}{a} \Rightarrow x = \frac{(a-b)b}{a}, \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{a-b}{y} = \frac{a}{c} \Rightarrow y = \frac{(a-b)c}{a}. \quad (11)$$

Summing the areas of all four right triangles described above, which form the square with side of length a , we get:

$$\frac{1}{2}ab + \frac{1}{2}(a-b)x + \frac{1}{2}a(a-x) + \frac{1}{2}cy = a^2. \quad (12)$$

Substituting formulas (10) and (11) into expression (12), we get:

$$\frac{1}{2}ab + \frac{1}{2}(a-b)\frac{(a-b)b}{a} + \frac{1}{2}(a^2 - ab + b^2) + \frac{1}{2}\frac{(a-b)c^2}{a} = a^2. \quad (13)$$

The algebraic calculations with expression (13) are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} a^2b + (a-b)^2b + (a^2 - ab + b^2)a + (a-b)c^2 &= 2a^3 \Rightarrow \\ a^2b + a^2b - 2ab^2 + b^3 + a^3 - a^2b + ab^2 + ac^2 - bc^2 &= 2a^3 \Rightarrow \\ a^2b - ab^2 + b^3 + a^3 + ac^2 - bc^2 &= 2a^3 \Rightarrow \\ b(a^2 + b^2 - c^2) + a(c^2 - a^2 - b^2) &= 0 \Rightarrow (c^2 - a^2 - b^2)(a-b) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

It follows from identity (14) that either $a = b$, or $c^2 = a^2 + b^2$, i.e. for the general case where $a \neq b$ Pythagorean Theorem is proved.

For the special case, it is proven as follows. Construct squares on the sides of the triangle with equal cathets, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Diagram for the third new proof of the Pythagorean Theorem in the special case when $a = b$

Let us denote the area of the original rectangle with equal cathets by S , then $c^2 = 4S$, $2a^2 = 4S$, i.e. Pythagoras' theorem for the special case $a^2 + a^2 = c^2$ is proved.

Proof 4. Now, consider the square constructed on the hypotenuse of length c (Fig. 4). From the similarity of triangles with areas S_1 and S_5 , we can determine the length of the cathetus z :

$$z = \frac{bc}{a}.$$

We can express the area of the square constructed on the hypotenuse of length c as:

$$c^2 = S_5 + S_1 + a^2 - S_1 - S_2 = a^2 + S_5 - S_2. \quad (15)$$

Substituting into expression (15) the values of the areas S_1 and S_5 of the corresponding right triangles, calculated by half products of their cathetus lengths, we obtain the following algebraic calculations:

$$\begin{aligned} c^2 &= a^2 + \frac{bc^2}{2a} - \frac{(a-b)^2 b}{2a} \Rightarrow 2c^2 a - c^2 b = 2a^3 - a^2 b + 2ab^2 - b^3 \\ &\Rightarrow c^2 (2a - b) = a^2 (2a - b) + b^2 (2a - b) \\ &\Rightarrow (c^2 - a^2 - b^2)(2a - b) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

From identity (16), we conclude that either $2a = b$ or $c^2 = a^2 + b^2$. Thus, for the general case when $2a \neq b$, the Pythagorean Theorem is proven.

For the proof of the special case, let us construct Figure 6.

Figure 6. Diagram for the fourth new proof of the Pythagorean Theorem in the special case when $2a = b$

In this case, the Pythagorean Theorem simplifies to the equality $a^2 + b^2 = c^2 \Rightarrow a^2 + 4a^2 = 5a^2 = c^2$. From Figure 6, we observe that the square constructed on the hypotenuse of length c consists of one square with area a^2 and four congruent right triangles, each with area

$$\frac{1}{2} \cdot a \cdot 2a = a^2 .$$

Thus, the equality $5a^2 = c^2$ holds.

Incidentally, Figure 6 is well-known in the literature related to the Pythagorean Theorem [1, 2]. As b approaches a , the inner square in Figure 6 collapses into a point, and this diagram degenerates into Figure 5. Both of the last two proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem are algebraic in nature.

As we can see, all four proofs, as well as most other proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem, use the triangle similarity theorem. Unlike the known proofs, our new proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem in the last two cases are reduced to the case where the product of two algebraic terms is zero. Equating the first term to zero reduces to proving the general case of the Pythagorean Theorem, and equating the second term to zero reduces to proving the special case, which is easy to prove.

Заклучение

Looking at various proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem, we can conclude that the main idea of many proofs is to construct a geometric figure based on the original right triangle, calculate its area in two different ways, and then arrive at the identity $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$. The missing segment lengths in this figure are usually determined from the similarity of the triangles.

The Pythagorean Theorem is a good example for teaching mathematics to schoolchildren and students because the number of proofs is not limited. Proofs of this theorem in different ways are very good algebro-geometric exercises. Schools and universities can organise competitions for the greatest number of proofs of the Pythagorean Theorem. These competitions could lead to new proofs of the theorem. All this could develop into a kind of movement called "Pythagoreana", which would be very useful in raising the prestige of mathematical education among young people.

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